

Report

Exemplary elements of data-fitness for FAIRness measurement templates

Milestone M3.3.3 (v1.0)

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Executive Summary

This report presents exemplary elements of **data fitness** required to construct FAIRness measurement templates within the FAIRagro context. Data fitness is understood as the degree to which data meet the requirements of a specific analytical, scientific, or operational use case. Within FAIRagro's Measure 3.3, these elements form a conceptual bridge between generic data quality standards and application-specific requirements arising from heterogeneous agrosystem datasets.

The work systematically derives data-fitness elements from two complementary perspectives: (1) a **producer-side conceptualization of data quality**, grounded in ISO technical standards, and (2) a **user-side, application-driven perspective**, extracted from domain literature describing fitness-for-purpose, which focuses on the context-dependent suitability of data for a specific application according to the user's functional requirements (Hedayat Mahmoudi & Möller, 2025). Rather than computing dataset-specific metrics, this milestone introduces an approach to identify *exemplary indicators and structural elements* that can be reused across datasets and applications.

Methodological contribution. This milestone introduces a reusable method for the identification and structuring of exemplary data-fitness elements. The method combines a schema-based interpretation of ISO 19157 with constrained, literature-driven semantic extraction to bridge producer-oriented data quality concepts and user-oriented fitness-for-purpose requirements. It is explicitly non-operational and focuses on defining *what types of information* are required for FAIRness assessment, rather than *how* data quality should be computed.

Both perspectives are integrated into a structured, machine-readable conceptual framework suitable for FAIRness measurement templates. An illustrative example schema demonstrates how these elements can be represented without reporting actual dataset results. The identified elements provide the conceptual foundation for subsequent FAIRagro's milestones M3.3.4–M3.3.6 (Ewert et al., 2023), which focus on operationalization, community discussion, and implementation of application-specific data quality queries. The identification and structuring of these elements is supported by a constrained, schema-based interpretation of standards and literature, combining automated semantic extraction with expert validation. This milestone is deliberately limited to conceptual identification and structuring of exemplary data-fitness elements and does not define operational metrics or assessment workflows.

1 Introduction

The concept of *data fitness* describes how well data satisfy the requirements of a specific analytical, scientific, or operational purpose (Lacagnina et al., 2022; Pôças et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2013). In agrosystem research, data fitness is particularly critical because datasets are highly heterogeneous with respect to spatial scale, temporal resolution, measurement practices, uncertainty characteristics, and documentation quality. Within FAIRagro, data fitness plays a central role in assessing FAIRness, especially along the **Reusability (R)** dimension (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Milestone M3.3.3 focuses on identifying *exemplary elements of data fitness* that can later be operationalized into FAIRness measurement templates and integrated into FAIRagro's quality assessment and discovery framework. These elements are not intended to replace existing standards or compute new quality metrics, but to clarify *what kinds of information* are required to judge whether data are fit for particular uses. To achieve this, we pursue a dual approach focussing on the identification and structuring of *exemplary data-fitness elements* using the example of a domain-specific use case in digital soil mapping (DSM) context:

1. First, we draw on **producer-side quality characteristics** defined by ISO standards, which describe intrinsic properties of data in a standardized and interoperable manner. On the producer

side, this work is exemplarily grounded in a structured interpretation of ISO 19157-1, 2023, resulting in a machine-readable conceptual backbone of standardized data quality elements and their relationships, which is used to systematically derive data-fitness elements without defining operational metrics.

2. Second, we incorporate **user-side, application-specific fitness-for-purpose factors** described in scientific literature, capturing contextual requirements that are often absent from standard metadata. By merging these perspectives, the report aims to represent both intrinsic data properties and contextual requirements of end users in a way that is fully compatible with FAIR principles.

ISO 19157-1, 2023 defines a comprehensive framework for describing geodata quality from a producer perspective (Brodeur et al., 2019). It specifies core quality elements such as completeness, logical consistency, positional accuracy, thematic accuracy, and temporal accuracy, as well as evaluation methods and reporting structures. The strength of ISO 19157-1, 2023 lies in its generality and stability, providing a shared vocabulary that supports interoperability across domains and infrastructures. At the same time, this generality implies that ISO 19157-1, 2023 deliberately avoids prescribing application-specific metrics, validation strategies, or uncertainty estimation methods. As a result, ISO-compliant quality information may be difficult for users to interpret when assessing fitness-for-purpose in concrete analytical scenarios.

Terminology and reporting practices vary widely across domains and applications. Consequently, user-relevant quality information is often present in publications and documentation but not readily accessible for automated FAIRness assessment or dataset discovery. There, data fitness from an application-driven perspective is described including the adequacy of spatial and temporal resolution, the completeness of required variables, validation approaches, uncertainty characteristics, and known limitations with respect to specific models or decision contexts. These descriptions are highly relevant for data reuse but are typically heterogeneous, implicit, and weakly standardized.

Within FAIRagro's Measure 3.3, there is a clear need to connect standardized, producer-oriented quality concepts with application-oriented fitness-for-purpose considerations. Identifying exemplary data-fitness elements that reconcile these perspectives is a prerequisite for:

- developing application-specific data quality queries (M3.3.4–M3.3.6),
- supporting quality-aware dataset discovery and recommendation (Measure 4.3), and
- extending FAIRagro's quality metadata descriptors (Measure 3.1).

This milestone therefore focuses on conceptual integration rather than implementation details, providing reusable building blocks for subsequent activities.

2 Methodology

To identify exemplary data-fitness elements for FAIRness measurement templates, we applied a **two-stage approach** that integrates both conceptual reasoning and practical extraction procedures. This methodology combines ISO 19157-based producer perspectives with literature-derived, user-oriented fitness-for-purpose criteria.

The methodology is deliberately scoped to the *conceptual identification and structuring* of exemplary data-fitness elements. While automated procedures are used to support systematic extraction and harmonization, the resulting elements are not operational metrics, nor do they prescribe assessment workflows. Instead, the methodology clarifies which types of quality- and fitness-related information are required to support FAIRness assessment and reuse decisions.

Figure 1: Conceptual workflow for identifying exemplary data-fitness elements, integrating ISO 19157–based producer-side quality concepts with literature-derived, user-oriented fitness-for-purpose considerations. Automated semantic extraction supports interpretation and structuring but does not define operational metrics.

2.1 Method Scope and Positioning

The methodology presented in this milestone constitutes a structured identification and integration method for exemplary data-fitness elements. It is designed to operate at the conceptual level and is intentionally separated from operational data quality assessment, metric computation, or workflow execution.

The method addresses the gap between standardized, producer-oriented quality frameworks and heterogeneous, application-driven fitness-for-purpose descriptions found in domain literature. It defines a reproducible procedure for:

1. extracting quality-related concepts from standards and literature,
2. semantically aligning these concepts across producer and user perspectives, and
3. organizing them into a machine-readable structure suitable for FAIRness measurement templates.

This methodological scope ensures reusability across datasets, domains, and applications, while leaving metric definition and assessment workflows to subsequent milestones. Automated semantic extraction is used exclusively as a support mechanism for systematic identification and structuring of concepts and does not replace expert interpretation or normative standard alignment.

2.2 Conceptual Framework: From ISO 19157 to Exemplary Data-Fitness Elements

This framework preserves the original semantics of ISO 19157-1, 2023, including *quality elements, evaluation methods, quality results, and metaquality dimensions*, and serves as a stable reference for defining data-fitness elements without prescribing operational metrics.

1. The first stage established a **conceptual foundation** by systematically interpreting ISO 19157-1, 2023. An automated processing pipeline combined structured document parsing with **large language model (LLM)-assisted semantic extraction and structuring** to reconstruct core entities, hierarchies, and relationships of the ISO data quality framework in a *machine-readable form*.
2. In the second stage, selected ISO 19157-based components were **selectively expanded with literature-derived operational interpretations**. Peer-reviewed studies, with a focus on quantitative spatial and environmental datasets, provided concrete validation strategies, accuracy measures, uncertainty estimation approaches, and reporting practices. These expansions remain semantically anchored to ISO 19157-1, 2023 concepts and do *not* alter the underlying standard.

The **outcome** is a collection of *illustrative data-fitness elements*, intended to guide FAIRness template design rather than to define mandatory metrics or workflows.

2.3 Practical Procedures: Extraction and Integration of Data-Fitness Elements

Large language models (LLMs) were used solely to assist in the extraction, structuring, and semantic organization of information from standards and scientific literature. They were not used to introduce new quality concepts, redefine ISO terminology, or derive assessment results. All outputs serve as conceptual guidance and are subsequently validated and aligned using expert-defined rules.

2.3.1 LLM-assisted semantic extraction and ISO 19157-aligned quality modeling

To enable a systematic and reproducible integration of literature-derived validation practices with the ISO 19157 data quality framework, we implemented a multi-stage extraction and classification workflow that combines constrained large language model (LLM) outputs with rule-based semantic modeling and expert-informed alignment logic.

The workflow is explicitly designed to separate *semantic extraction* from *normative standard interpretation*. In particular, the LLM is used exclusively for controlled information extraction and preliminary semantic characterization, while all ISO 19157 alignment decisions are performed deterministically outside the model.

Input normalization. Scientific articles and standards documents are converted from PDF into a structured Markdown representation that preserves narrative text, tables, figures, captions, and image references. This representation provides explicit structural cues (e.g. section headers, lists, and figure anchors) that support robust downstream semantic extraction.

LLM-constrained semantic extraction. A large language model is prompted under strict schema constraints to extract validation-relevant entities from the input documents, including quantitative validation metrics, validation strategies, uncertainty estimation methods, and reporting requirements. The LLM output is required to conform exactly to a predefined typed schema, enforcing structured fields for metric identity, semantic role, evaluation target, result nature, supporting evidence, and extraction confidence. The model is explicitly prohibited from introducing new terminology, redefining ISO concepts, or asserting compliance with the standard.

Semantic classification independent of ISO. Extracted elements are subsequently enriched using deterministic classification rules that assign semantic properties such as metric value type (e.g. scalar, graphical, or distributional), evaluation target (e.g. attribute value, prediction interval, or full predictive distribution), and functional role (e.g. primary measurement, validation indicator, or diagnostic). These classifications describe the functional behavior of each metric independently of any standard.

Expert-driven conceptual taxonomy. In a separate step, expert-defined logic assigns each extracted element to a conceptual quality category (e.g. point prediction accuracy, reliability, calibration, or uncertainty characterization) and to a higher-level quality dimension (e.g. accuracy, reliability, or uncertainty quality). These conceptual categories may extend beyond the expressiveness of ISO 19157 and are treated as non-normative constructs.

Rule-based ISO 19157 alignment and extension. ISO 19157 alignment is performed only after semantic and expert classification. Each extracted element is assigned one of three alignment types: *ISO-native* (explicitly defined in the standard), *ISO-crosswalk* (conceptually compatible but not explicitly defined), or *ISO-extension* (outside the current scope of ISO 19157). Alignment candidates are generated using explicit rules based on evaluation target, result nature, and semantic role, and are associated with a confidence score reflecting the strength of the conceptual correspondence. Elements that cannot be normatively placed are preserved as structured extensions rather than forced into ISO categories.

Taxonomy construction and validation. The final output of the workflow is a machine-readable, hierarchical quality taxonomy rooted in the ISO 19157 `QualityElement` structure. ISO-native elements remain unchanged, while crosswalked and extended elements are explicitly marked and traceable to their source evidence. All placements are validated against the standard, and ambiguous cases are resolved through expert review.

Role of the large language model. The LLM operates strictly below the level of standard interpretation. It does not introduce new quality concepts, redefine ISO terminology, infer standard compliance, or assess data quality. Its role is limited to scalable, evidence-backed semantic extraction under schema and terminology constraints. This design ensures that the resulting taxonomy remains normative, transparent, and reproducible, while enabling systematic integration of contemporary validation practices that are not explicitly covered by ISO 19157.

2.3.2 Extraction of Producer-Side Quality Characteristics

As an example of an existing data quality standard, ISO 19157-1, 2023 was analyzed to identify *intrinsic dataset properties*. Two high-level categories were distinguished:

1. **Data Quality Elements:** Properties directly describing data, including positional accuracy, temporal accuracy, thematic accuracy, completeness, and logical consistency.
2. **Non-Quantitative Quality Elements:** Contextual descriptors such as lineage, purpose, usage constraints, maintenance information, and documentation quality.

These elements were further subdivided into thematic sub-elements (e.g., classification correctness, omissions errors, domain consistency, topological consistency, timestamp correctness). A **language-model-assisted workflow** supported the conversion of ISO conceptual content into a structured, machine-readable form.

2.3.3 Extraction of User-specific fitness-for-purpose Elements

To complement producer-side characteristics, we reviewed *domain literature* addressing application-driven data fitness. Relevant indicators include:

- Completeness of variables required by a specific application,
- Adequacy of spatial, temporal, and thematic resolution,
- Accuracy requirements determined by model sensitivity,
- Consistency of measurement and processing methods across datasets,
- Reliability and trustworthiness of data sources,
- Accessibility, licensing, and usability considerations,
- Spatial uncertainty

These elements highlight *contextual requirements* often absent from standardized metadata and inform the inclusion of user-oriented fitness indicators.

2.3.4 Semantic Alignment and Expert Validation

All extracted producer- and user-side elements undergo a semantic alignment step to ensure consistency across perspectives. This includes harmonization of terminology, assignment to ISO 19157 quality elements where applicable, and explicit marking of concepts that extend beyond the ISO standard (e.g. application-specific uncertainty indicators). Automated suggestions are systematically checked against expert-defined mappings, and corrections are applied where necessary.

This alignment step ensures that the resulting conceptual schema remains interoperable, reproducible, and suitable for machine-readable FAIRness templates, while still accommodating domain-specific interpretations of data fitness.

2.3.5 Integration and Conceptual Schema Construction

Producer- and user-side elements were integrated into a **unified conceptual schema** representing data fitness at multiple levels. The schema is:

- **Machine-readable** Supports FAIRness template development,
- **Reusable across datasets** Independent of specific metric values,
- **Descriptive rather than evaluative** Specifies *what* should be described rather than *how well* a dataset performs.

3 Digital Soil Mapping Use Case

The reputation of data providers and the accuracy of geodata are critical factors for the trustworthiness of digital soil mapping (DSM) products. Although there are established DSM procedures (e.g., Ma et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2017), validation practices in DSM studies often lack consideration of the intended application (Piikki et al., 2021; Schmidinger & Heuvelink, 2023).

Figure 2 illustrates a typical digital soil mapping (DSM) workflow highlighting three main phases: parametrization, feature engineering, and modeling:

1. Parametrization combines soil samples and explaining covariates like soil reflectance composites, and terrain attributes as the core input data sources.

Figure 2: Typical DSM workflow steps delineating three fundamental phases Parametrization, Feature Engineering, and modeling (Möller et al., 2022). RU – Reference Units, RFE – Recursive Feature Elimination, SCMaP-SRC – Satellite-based Soil Reflectance Composites derived by the SCMaP algorithm (Rogge et al., 2018).

Figure 3: Test site location in Bavaria and the distribution of soil samples (Möller et al., 2022; Zepp et al., 2023) (a) and the spatial distribution of test and training data (b).

(a) External validation metrics based in test samples: $R^2 = 0.81$ and $RMSE = 1.69$

Figure 4: SOC content prediction result (a) and corresponding uncertainty layers Prediction Interval Width (*PIW*) and Dissimilarity Index (*DI*) in Bavaria.

Table 1: Expert-based enhancement of standardized ISO 19157-1, 2023 data quality categories for the metrics *R*², *Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)*, *Prediction Interval Width (PIW)* and *Dissimilarity Index (DI)*.

Metric	Scale	Source	Data Quality Taxonomy Levels	
			1	2
<i>R</i> ²	global	ISO 19157-1, 2023	Thematic Quality	Quantitative Attribute Accuracy
<i>RMSE</i>	global	ISO 19157-1, 2023	Thematic Quality	Quantitative Attribute Accuracy
<i>PIW</i>	local	Piikki et al., 2021	Spatial Uncertainty	Numerical Spatial Uncertainty
<i>DI</i>	local	Meyer et al., 2025	Spatial Uncertainty	Numerical Spatial Uncertainty

2. Feature engineering covers data splitting, sampling design, and covariate selection (here, recursive feature elimination), preparing predictors that are subsequently used in the machine-learning phase.
3. The modeling phase then comprises model training, spatial prediction, external validation, and the derivation of uncertainty information.

The SOCastR workflow implements this conceptual framework through sequential processing steps, organized into initialization and data preparation, model development and validation, and production prediction with dual uncertainty quantification (Möller, 2025). The workflow has been applied using the example of a Bavarian test site (Figure 3a) and a soil organic carbon (SOC) content prediction exercise. Figure 3b shows both the spatial distribution of soil samples and the partitioning into training and test sets, which is essential for independent performance assessment. The prediction outputs and quality information are shown in Figure 4. The SOC map in Figure 4a is accompanied by global accuracy metrics based on the external test set ($R^2 = 0.81$, $RMSE = 1.69$) providing a summary of overall model performance.

Figure 4b and Figure 4c extend this producer-specific view by adding spatially explicit uncertainty information:

- Generated through Quantile Regression Forest (QRF; Meinshausen, 2006), the **Prediction Interval Width (PIW)** map quantifies model-based uncertainty by computing the difference between the 95th and 5th percentile predictions (Q95 - Q05), providing a 90% prediction interval at each spatial location. This metric captures the inherent variability in SOC predictions arising from data noise, measurement error, and natural heterogeneity in the soil-environment relationship.
- Computed using the CAST package's AOA methodology (Meyer et al., 2025), the **Dissimilarity Index (DI)** represents distance-based uncertainty by quantifying the multivariate distance from each prediction pixel to its nearest training sample in feature space. High *DI* values indicate extrapolation beyond the training domain, signaling regions where predictions may revert to training data means and should be interpreted with caution or excluded from decision-making.

Table 2 summarizes all quality metrics. R^2 and *RMSE* align with ISO 19157-1, 2023 as instances of thematic quality, specifically quantitative attribute accuracy, whereas *PIW* and *DI* are classified as local spatial uncertainty metrics derived from literature and representing domain-specific common practice. Together, these layers form a two-dimensional quality description: standardized aggregated metrics on the one hand, and domain-specific spatial uncertainty on the other.

Table 2: Hierarchical organization of producer-side data quality elements according to ISO 19157-1, 2023.

Main Element	Sub-element
DataEvaluation	IndirectEvaluation
	FullInspection
	SampleBasedInspection
QualityElement	MeasureReference
	EvaluationMethod
	QualityResult
QualityResult	CoverageResult
	ConformanceResult
	QuantitativeResult
	DescriptiveResult
Metaquality	Confidence
	Representativity
	Homogeneity
Completeness	Commission
	Omission
LogicalConsistency	ConceptualConsistency
	DomainConsistency
	FormatConsistency
	TopologicalConsistency
PositionalAccuracy	AbsolutePositionalAccuracy
	RelativePositionalAccuracy
	GriddedDataPositionalAccuracy
ThematicQuality	ThematicClassificationCorrectness
	NonQuantitativeAttributeCorrectness
	QuantitativeAttributeAccuracy
TemporalQuality	AccuracyOfATimeMeasurement
	TemporalValidity
	TemporalConsistency

4 Results

4.1 Producer-Side Data Quality Characteristics

Data quality characteristics on the producer side are structured according to ISO 19157-1, 2023, which defines intrinsic properties that describe the dataset's measurable quality. Table 2 summarizes the main elements and their sub-elements. In addition to these standardized, quantitative elements, non-quantitative descriptors such as lineage, usage constraints, and maintenance information—provide essential context for interpreting data and supporting reuse.

4.2 User-Side Data Fitness Indicators

Application-specific fitness indicators complement the ISO framework by capturing the dataset's suitability for intended analytical or operational purposes. These indicators extend ISO concepts with practical metrics and contextual criteria, including accuracy, reliability, calibration, sharpness, and uncertainty evaluation. Table 3 presents probabilistic metrics classified by expert categories and

Table 3: Probabilistic metrics: expert classification with ISO 19157 alignment.

Expert Category	Metric	Expert Subcategory / Role	ISO Alignment
Accuracy	ME	BiasDetection (primary)	ThematicQuality / QuantitativeAttributeAccuracy
	RMSE	ErrorMagnitude (primary)	ThematicQuality / QuantitativeAttributeAccuracy
	MEC	ModelSkill (summary)	ThematicQuality / QuantitativeAttributeAccuracy
Reliability Calibration	PICP	PredictionIntervalCoverage (primary)	Metaquality / Confidence, Probabilistic
	QCP	QuantileCalibration (primary)	Metaquality / Confidence, Probabilistic
	PIT Histogram	DistributionConsistency (diagnostic)	Distributional consistency / graphical diagnostic
	RELI	DistributionalCalibration (summary)	Derived from CRPS / IS decomposition
Sharpness Proper Scoring	PIW	IntervalWidth (primary)	QualityResult / Sharpness
	IS	IntervalScoring (complementary)	QualityResult / Proper Scoring
	CRPS	DistributionalAccuracy (primary)	QualityResult / Proper Scoring
Diagnostic	BIAS	BiasDetection (diagnostic)	One-sided bias detection

aligned with ISO 19157, extracted from (Schmidinger & Heuvelink, 2023) via an LLM-assisted workflow, providing a bridge between standardized quality elements and user-focused evaluation.

In addition to these metrics, user-oriented fitness considerations include the relevance of variables for specific applications, adequacy of spatial, temporal, and thematic resolution, consistency of measurement and processing methods across datasets, reliability and trustworthiness of sources, and accessibility or licensing constraints. Together, these indicators ensure that datasets are not only intrinsically accurate but also contextually fit for intended analytical or operational purposes, aligning with FAIR principles.

4.3 Integrated Multi-Layer Framework

By combining producer-side ISO elements with user-side fitness indicators, a multi-layer conceptual structure emerges:

- **Intrinsic Data Quality (Producer):** standardized, measurable properties defined by ISO 19157.
- **Contextual Fitness (User):** application-oriented suitability and operational relevance of the dataset.
- **Metadata Completeness:** availability of lineage, methodological, and usage information supporting interpretation, reuse, and reproducibility.

This integrated framework provides a structured foundation for developing FAIRness measurement templates and supports the systematic identification of exemplary data-fitness elements across datasets and applications.

5 Discussion

Methodological Contribution. Beyond the identification of exemplary data-fitness elements, this milestone contributes a generalizable method for bridging producer-side data quality standards

and user-side fitness-for-purpose requirements. The method demonstrates how ISO 19157 concepts can be systematically interpreted, extended, and contextualized using literature-derived knowledge while preserving semantic alignment and interoperability. This approach provides a scalable foundation for FAIRness template design and quality-aware dataset discovery without constraining future operational implementations.

The identified exemplary elements enable FAIRagro to conceptualize data fitness in a way that is both technically grounded and practically relevant. ISO-based quality elements provide standardized and interoperable descriptors, while literature-derived fitness-for-purpose indicators ensure that application context and user requirements are explicitly represented.

By focusing on exemplary elements rather than computed metrics, this milestone provides flexible building blocks that can be adapted across domains, datasets, and applications. The approach supports automated FAIRness assessment, quality-aware dataset discovery, and the formulation of application-specific queries in later project phases.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

This report identifies exemplary elements of data fitness relevant to FAIRness measurement templates within FAIRagro (M3.3.3). By integrating producer-side ISO 19157-based quality concepts with user-side fitness-for-purpose considerations from domain literature, it provides a structured conceptual foundation for application-oriented data quality assessment.

The identified elements directly support subsequent milestones:

- **M3.3.4:** definition of typical application-related data quality queries,
- **M3.3.5:** community discussion and refinement of quality metrics,
- **M3.3.6:** operationalization of data-fitness elements in FAIRagro services.

The exemplary data-fitness elements identified in this milestone directly feed into subsequent FAIRagro's activities, in particular the formulation of application-specific data quality queries (M3.3.4), their discussion and refinement with domain communities (M3.3.5), and their operationalization within FAIRagro's services and assessment workflows (M3.3.6).

Together with D3.3.1, this milestone establishes the conceptual groundwork for scalable, FAIR-aligned, and application-aware data quality and fitness assessment in agrosystem research.

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